

Is Employment Empowering Women? an Analysis of Selected Case Studies of Internal Migrated Women in Dhaka City

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ABSTRACT

In Bangladesh, there is the rapid growth of urbanization. Consequently, job opportunity is also increasing in a different economic sector in urban areas. In recent years the growth of female migration is significantly increasing. Internal migration is one of the important factors of improvement of the socio-economic status of women. Migration and women empowerment are interrelated. Because of both push and pull factor, internal migration is increasing in the urban area. Dhaka is one of the fastest growing megacities in the world. Internal migration, that is to say, rural to urban migration of women and is engaging in income-generating activities have an impact on their lives and livelihood.

Keyword: Migration, Empowerment, Employment, Urbanization

1. INTRODUCTION

Internal Migration refers to movement from one household to another household in a different compound, home or homestead within the Demographic Surveillance Area. Bangladesh is currently facing huge challenges of rapid urbanization. The rate of growth of urban population is likely to fall to some extent in the future, but would still be quite high. The UN projection for the urban population of Bangladesh for 2030 was 86.5 million. The proportion of urban would possibly cross the 50% mark by 2040 and the 60% mark by the year 2050 when the total urban population would rise above 100 million. The city of Dhaka in recent years has emerged as one of the fastest rapid growing cities in the world.

According to the Global Economic Forum, Global Gender Gap Index Bangladesh has come forward as

the 2nd best-ranked country in Asia in the terms of gender equality. Climbing places from last year Bangladesh has cemented the 47th in the rank globally. According to the report, Bangladesh has made a massive improvement in creating equal opportunity.

The current global trend knows a massive expansion of urban areas, this growth being actually generated by the numerical population growth and migration. Urban development determines changes regarding the organization of places, economic and social changes but these effects exceed the territorial barriers and generate a broad impact. Urbanization is seen as an effect of the current globalization phenomenon, with social aspects as well as the economic ones, representing the migration process of the population organizing in urban areas, areas considered to be true centers of progress that offer multiple options to residents. Cities are centers of changes, placed in a relationship of interdependence with demographic growth and economic growth. Substantial expansion of urban areas is due population migration to these areas, the identification of new feature options that can ensure the raising of welfare levels of individuals and improve their conditions of life. Internal migration has a large history in Bangladesh though data is unavailable. As Bangladesh is a disaster-prone country (Hossain and Ferdousi, 2004). From rural area migrating to Dhaka city to get a job, improve their socio-economic status. The size of the female labor force in Bangladesh increased at a significantly more rapid rate than that of men from the 2015-16 fiscal year to FY2016-17. According to a report from the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, the size of the female labor force increased by 4.6%, while the male labor force increased by 1%. The total labor force

increased by 1.4 million, or 2.3%. According to the Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies, in 1974 women participation in the labor force was 4% but it has increased to 35.6 percent in 2016.

2. Methods

The aim of this research is to understand the changes of women lives due to Internal migration and would like to explore its impact on women socio-economic condition from the perspective of the concept of economic empowerment. In-depth interviews with guideline have been used for data collection. There were 10 female those who are migrated in Dhaka more than 5-10 years living in Aftabnagar, Badda, Dholaiapar area. In-depth interviews with guideline have been used for data collection. This study is limited by selected working women who were living in Dholaiapar, Badda and Aftabnagar area for 5-10 years.

3. Literature Review

The situations of the garment factory workers also provided the evidence between the link of migration and poverty (Afsar, R .2003) Rural-Urban migration, the most crucial component of internal migration of any country, is a powerful symbol for regional inequality, in terms of economy, opportunities and living standards (Islam 2006).

Migration is often considered as a driver of growth and an important route out of poverty with a significant positive impact on people's livelihoods and wellbeing (Anh, 2003). Rural-urban migration in less developed countries depends on the difference in expected wage from migration (urban wage) versus an agricultural wage. (Todaro, 1969 and Harris and Todaro 1970).Migrants often benefited more than non-migrants because of their innovative, risk-taking and desperate nature. (Afsar, R .2000)

The direct and indirect factors were available with a gaze at the impact of internal migration on poverty mitigation. For example, the headcount index, in addition to the unemployment rates and the increase in income in case of poor urban households illustrated a definite inclination of poverty decline and enhanced economic conditions. About 6.7 percent annual growth rate was contrasting to 3.4 percent per capita enlargement for rural incomes. Because of poverty and lack of employment major reasons for out-migration opportunity. (Rahman et al.1996). The land is an important factor in Bangladesh. A landless

family took their decision for migration more often comparing those with the land. Bangladesh is a reverie country where the flood is a recurring theme. The population mobility regained in these recent years towards Dhaka city in case of the vulnerable ecology seasonal migration was more common livelihood strategy in West Bengal among the poorest people who were usually most affected by these natural disasters.(Rogaly and Rafique 2003) Seasonal migration is for most of those involved, a way of hanging on. For a small minority of migrants with a land, supportive family structures, other social assets and/or other sources of income, remittances may remain available for investment in agriculture or to make an impression through conspicuous consumption. (Rogaly and Rafique, 2003). Living condition advantage of rural-urban migrants and urban natives over rural-natives primarily linked to migration selectivity by education and occupation. Once the independent effects of education and occupation are controlled, an association between migration status and living conditions remain significant but living condition advantage of rural-urban migrants and urban natives over rural natives fall down. (Haque M. Ershadul and Islam M. Mazharul. 2012) Migration was an important strategy for the poor people in Bangladesh for their livelihood. Rural-urban migrant had a lower level of association with better living condition compared with urban natives. But educated and professional/housewife migrants' lead better household living conditions. (Haque& Islam, 2012)

4. Findings & Discussion

4.1 Job History

All the women those who interviewed have occupied / involve in income-earning activities. Most of them were not engaged in cash income in rural area. After they migrated Dhaka city are working women in different sectors like housemaid, garments worker, cleaner, messenger, day labor. But before migration they were unemployed. Because of rapid growth of urbanization in Dhaka city there are plenty of working opportunity for women. So they have a specific monthly income.. The average income of the respondent is 5000 BDT. Most of the respondents are not satisfied. Please find the details of respondents income and occupation in Table 1.

4.2 Migration History

Out of 10 interviewed migrated women those who migrated from rural to the urban area given some

different background. After finishing her graduation Yesmin came to Dhaka to find a job. She was unemployed and didn't have any income. So she decided to migrate to Dhaka where she can get a job and earn money. Monoara Begum's son was suffering from an illness. She came to Dhaka to just visit a doctor for her son. And because of the circumstance during that time she decided to stay permanently in Dhaka. Nasima Khatun migrated to Dhaka city after she got married. As her husband was living in Dhaka city she had to move from her village. Rehana Parvin migrated to Dhaka city as she wanted to do a job in Dhaka city and as she said, she doesn't like to live in the village because of the absence of facilities, working opportunities. Rekha, migrated to Dhaka City because of poverty. She was sent by his family in Dhaka to work as a housemaid in a family. Later after a couple of years, she started to work in a garments factory. Shahnaz she lost her home because of river erosion. Every year in Bangladesh people lost their home because of riverbank erosion and like Shahtaz people migrate to Dhaka city. Asha got tortured by her mother in laws after marriage. She didn't get any support from her husband. So she ran away from a place and came to Dhaka city to get rid of all family disturbance. Asma Sharmin came to Dhaka city in the search of her father who left them while back and also improve their financial condition. Ayesha Akhter migrated to Dhaka city 16 years ago from Khulna. She came to Dhaka city with her husband after she got married. Amena Ahmed, migrated to Dhaka city because of poverty. Most of the time she was starving while she was living in a village. After migrating to Dhaka she works in as a helping hand in different houses.

4.3 Expenditures & Lifestyle

4.3.1 Most spent sector:

Most of the women spend their income on their children educational expenses, food, rent. Apart from that Asma Sharmin pays her own tuition fees for her education and also supports her family. Monoara Begum supports her daughter family and saving

money from her income thinking of her old age security.

4.3.2 Improvement of the family:

Most of the respondent was unemployed when they were in the village. After migration, they started to work and income money. Because living in Dhaka city is very much expensive so they face trouble in their lives. Shahtaz used to live in Gaibandha but because of river erosion she lost her home and she migrated to Dhaka city. She is still struggling with her family. Meanwhile, Rehana Parvin family condition has improved after migrating to Dhaka city. She is living in a comfortable residence. The money she earned is well enough to support her family. Because of her contribution her family has a comfortable life. Please find the details of future aspiration and job satisfaction of respondents in Table 2.

5. Concluding Remarks

In Bangladesh, poverty is considered as one of the key drivers of the rural-urban migration. Poverty, lack of work availability, unemployment, natural disaster and socio-cultural factors like marriage, family conflict, better educational opportunities etc are among the most dominating factors in the last few decades internal migration of women in Dhaka city is increasing. (Rahman. M & Chowdhury. S). In villages there are lacks of working opportunity. So most women are coming to Dhaka city to improve economic condition, support their family. In village most of the women were unemployed but after migration they started to income by engaging in different working sector. Women are stated to start up new business by their own, they are enter into different job sector (garments factory, cleaner, messenger) and there is a change have found due to internal migration in terms of their income condition, reduction of poverty, housing, children education. Because of internal migration (rural to urban) women economic condition has been changed because of their income and activities as a garments factory worker, messenger, housemaid, cleaner.

Annex

Table1. Income & Occupations of respondents

Cases	Income	Occupation
Case 1 (Yesmin)	6000 BDT	Messenger
Case 2 (Monoara Begum)	4500 BDT	Housemaid/ Cleaner
Case 3 (Nasima Khatun)	8000 BDT	Part time house maid
Case 4 (Rehana Parvin)	9772 BDT	Messenger
Case 5 (Rekha)	7000 BDT	Garments worker
Case 6 (Shahtaz)	6000 BDT	Day labor
Case 7 (Asha)	5000 BDT	Rubber factory worker
Case 8 (Asma Sharmin)	6000-7000 BDT	Messenger
Case 9 (Ayesha Akhter)	4000-5000 BDT	Cleaner
Case 10 (Amena Ahmed)	4500-5000 BDT	Housemaid

Table2. Future aspiration and Job satisfaction of respondents

Cases	Future Aspiration	Job Satisfaction
Case 1 (Yesmin)	Want to do a Government job	No
Case 2 (Monoara Begum)	Give her grandchildren proper education	Satisfied
Case 3 (Nasima Khatun)	Open up a farm	Satisfied
Case 4 (Rehana Parvin)	None	Full
Case 5 (Rekha)	Educate her child properly.	No
Case 6 (Shahtaz)	Want to start a new business	No
Case 7 (Asha)	Plan to open a “Tong” (shop) in future in Dhaka.	No
Case 8 (Asma Sharmin)	Wants to be a banker after finishing her graduation.	No
Case 9 (Ayesha Akhter)	Secure her children future and want my own home in village	No
Case 10 (Amena Ahmed)	Build a house in village	No

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